

IDENTIFICATION OF KEY BIOMETRIC RISK DIMENSIONS RELATED TO OBESITY AND BLOOD PRESSURE: A PCA-BASED STUDY

A.K.K.K. Athukorala

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, University of Colombo

ABSTRACT

Obesity is a global health concern which leads to a lot of non-communicable diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia, sleep disorders, cancers, and cardiovascular diseases by impacting mortality. [4] Hypertension is persistent elevation of arterial pressure and a major risk factor for heart, brain, kidney and other diseases. [8] The 6 variables are selected related to obesity and blood pressure in this study. The obesity measurements are weight, height, waist circumference and hip circumference. The blood pressure measurements are mean systolic blood pressure and mean diastolic blood pressure readings. The secondary data of 501300 women in India was used in this study. The well-known dimension reduction technique called Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is utilized in this study to identify the two biometric risk indices from these variables. PCA is applied in several fields for identifying key dimensions of health data such as dietary patterns, cardiovascular risk calculation and biometric data. [2][3][6] As a pre-requisite to PCA, Bartlett's test and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test were performed to check the correlation criteria and sampling adequacy. [10] The variance of the data is maximized in PCA and 1st PC is worked on the entire variance of the data set. [9] The extractions of variance to the 2nd PC by variables weight, height, waist circumference, hip circumference, mean systolic blood pressure reading and mean diastolic blood pressure reading are 81.7%, 21.2%, 79.6%, 82.6%, 84.7% and 85.3% respectively. In this study, the six principal components are extracted 48.315%, 24.209%, 15.330%, 4.640%, 4.390% 3.115% of variance respectively. The graphical representation of eigen values versus component numbers is called as scree plot which commonly practiced to identify the number of extracted principal components. [7] The 70% of cumulative variance is exceeded by 2nd PC and the eigen value is greater than one only for first two principal components in this study. Therefore these 6 variables can be compressed by using 2 principal components. The interpretation of extracted principal components can be well explained by rotated component matrix. Moreover, the variables represented relatively high values of this rotated component matrix are key factors. In this study, PC 1 represents obesity data and PC 2 represents blood pressure measurements. It can be verified by the data point clusters of component plot in rotated space. Eventually, these two key biometric risk dimensions can be applied to model the health risk.

Keywords: Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO), Principal Component (PC), Correlation, Obesity, Blood Pressure

Introduction

The human body size plays a vital role in health concerns of human beings. The body size classification can be quantified by using two standard measurements: body mass index (BMI) and waist to hip ratio (WHR). The BMI value is calculated dividing the weight (in kilo grams) of a person by the squared of the height (in meters). The WHR is the ratio between the waist & hip circumferences. The classification of body size according to the BMI is demonstrated in table 1.1 and the classification of health risk according to the WHR is illustrated in table 1.2. [1] Therefore, the

significance of bio metric measurements which leads to obesity such as weight, height, waist circumference and hip circumference can be clearly identified.

Body Mass Index	Body size
≤ 18.49	Under-weight
18.50 – 24.99	Healthy-weight
25.00 – 29.99	Over-weight
≥ 30	Obese

Table 1.1: Body mass index classification

Waist to Hip Ratio	Health risk
≤ 0.79	Low risk
0.80 – 0.84	Moderate risk
≥ 0.85	High risk

Table 1.2: Waist to hip ratio classification

The human blood pressure is measured in two values: systolic and diastolic. The blood pressure reading represents the force on artery walls in two moments: when the heart is squeezed to pump out the blood and the relax stage. [4] The systolic reading is the pressure on artery walls when the heart beats and pumps blood out. The diastolic reading is the pressure on artery walls when the heart relaxes between the beats. The systolic and diastolic blood pressure reading of a healthy person is around $120mmHg$ and $80mmHg$. [3] The classification of health risk according to the blood pressure levels is shown in table 1.3. [5] Therefore, several health concerns with obesity are associated with blood pressure readings. [8]

Category	Systolic ($mmHg$)	Diastolic ($mmHg$)	Health risk
Normal	< 120	< 80	Baseline risk
Elevated	120 – 129	< 80	Increased future risk
Stage 1 hypertension	130 – 139	80 – 89	Moderate cardiovascular risk
Stage 2 hypertension	≥ 140	≥ 90	High risk of complications

Table 1.3: Systolic & diastolic blood pressure classification

In this study, PCA is used to identify two main scores which reflect body size and blood pressure instead of these 6 variables. PCA is well known dimension reduction technique used in several fields: computer science, health science, data science, engineering etc. [6][7][9] This technique is widely explained under methodology.

Objectives

The objectives of this study can be listed as follows.

- To examine the correlation structure among anthropometric and blood pressure variables.
- To apply Principal Component Analysis to extract a smaller number of latent biometric components that summarize the shared variability among the six biometric variables.
- To determine the proportion of total variance explained by the extracted principal components and assess their adequacy using eigenvalues and cumulative variance criteria.
- To interpret the extracted principal components in terms of meaningful biometric constructs such as body size related and blood pressure related dimensions.
- To construct composite biometric indices based on the retained principal components for potential use in further health risk modeling.

Methodology

The main analysis technique of this study is principal component analysis. As a pre-requisite to PCA, Bartlett's test and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test were performed to check the correlation criteria and sampling adequacy. [10]

In PCA, the direction of maximum variance of the data set is found. [2] Therefore, the covariance matrix of the data set is maximized by using the Lagrange multiplier method. This mathematical simplification identifies the significant dimensions according descending order of variance. [3]

Results & Discussion

The table 4.1 shows the correlation matrix of six anthropometric and blood pressure variables. There is a high correlation between the variables: weight, waist circumference and hip circumference in anthropometric measurements and mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure readings.

	Weight	Height	Waist circumference	Hip circumference	Mean_SysBP	Mean_DiasBP
Correlation Weight	1.000	.342	.719	.740	.237	.270
Height	.342	1.000	.150	.200	.038	.018
Waist circumference	.719	.150	1.000	.808	.229	.269
Hip circumference	.740	.200	.808	1.000	.186	.250
Mean_SysBP	.237	.038	.229	.186	1.000	.722
Mean_DiasBP	.270	.018	.269	.250	.722	1.000

Table 4.1: Correlation matrix of six variables

The statistical significance of using PCA is showed in table 4.2 with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's test results. The KMO measure is 0.697 which is greater than 0.6 indicates the adequacy of PCA. Since the significant value is less than 0.05, the variables are correlated and PCA can be applied to identify the latent variables.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.697
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1471735.826
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

Table 4.2: KMO and Bartlett's test results

The extraction of variance of PC 1 and PC 2 can be demonstrated by 1st and 2nd columns of table 4.3. Since the PC 1 extracted the entire variance of each variable, it shows as 100% in the 1st column. The extractions of variance to the PC 2 by variable weight, height, waist circumference, hip circumference, mean systolic blood pressure reading and mean diastolic blood pressure reading are 81.7%, 21.2%, 79.6%, 82.6%, 84.7% and 85.3% respectively. The contribution of height is negligible and it can be verified by the high correlation only among weight, waist circumference and hip circumference of anthropometric measurements.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Weight	1.000	.817
Height	1.000	.212
Waist circumference	1.000	.796
Hip circumference	1.000	.826
Mean_SysBP	1.000	.847
Mean_DiasBP	1.000	.853

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4.3: Communalities table

Figure 4.1: Variance contribution to the PC 2

The variance and eigen values of all six principal components are shown in table 4.4. The six principal components are extracted 48.315%, 24.209%, 15.330%, 4.640%, 4.390% 3.115% of variance respectively. The 70% of cumulative variance is exceeded by 2nd PC and the eigen value is greater than one only for first two principal components. Therefore these 6 variables can be compressed by using 2 principal components. The extracted number of principal components is determined based on eigenvalues and cumulative variance criteria. The graphical representation of eigen values (scree plot) and variance extracted by each PC is demonstrated by figure 4.2 and figure 4.3 respectively.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.899	48.315	48.315	2.899	48.315	48.315	2.545	42.409	42.409
2	1.453	24.209	72.525	1.453	24.209	72.525	1.807	30.116	72.525
3	.920	15.330	87.855						
4	.278	4.640	92.495						
5	.263	4.390	96.885						
6	.187	3.115	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4.4: Variance and eigen values of principal components

Figure 4.2: Scree plot

Figure 4.3: Variance & Cumulative variance of PC

The component score coefficients are demonstrated in table 4.5 and standardized variables notations are mentioned in table 4.6. The PC 1 and PC 2 scores can be written as equation 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. In these two equations, the coefficients are multiplied by the standardized variable values in order to overcome the effect of different scales of variables. The standardized variables are calculated as equation 4.3 where x_i, μ_i and σ_i are represented the raw data value, mean and standard deviation of i th variable.

Component Score Coefficient Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Weight	.351	-.015
Height	.209	-.137
Waist circumference	.340	.002
Hip circumference	.358	-.030
Mean_SysBP	-.107	.545
Mean_DiasBP	-.085	.536

Table 4.5: Component score coefficient matrix

Symbol	Description
z_1	Standardized weight
z_2	Standardized height
z_3	Standardized waist circumference
z_4	Standardized hip circumference
z_5	Standardized mean systolic blood pressure
z_6	Standardized mean diastolic blood pressure

Table 4.6: Standardized variable notations

$$PC\ 1 = 0.351z_1 + 0.209z_2 + 0.340z_3 + 0.358z_4 - 0.107z_5 - 0.085z_6 \quad (4.1)$$

$$PC\ 2 = -0.015z_1 - 0.137z_2 + 0.002z_3 - 0.030z_4 + 0.545z_5 + 0.536z_6 \quad (4.2)$$

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} \quad (4.3)$$

Although the component loadings matrix is not commonly used for interpretation in PCA, the significance variables are clearly emphasized by the rotated component matrix. The component loading matrix in general space and rotated space are shown in table 4.7 and table 4.8 respectively. In the PC 1 column of table 4.8, weight, waist circumference and hip circumference are having comparatively high values among 6 variables. Therefore, it can be interpreted that the PC 1 represent body size measures. In the PC 2 column of table 4.8, mean systolic and diastolic measurements are having

relatively high values among 6 variables. Therefore, it can be interpreted that the PC 2 represent blood pressure measures. It can be verified by the clustered data points in component plot in rotated space shown in figure 4.4.

Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Weight	.862	-.271
Height	.329	-.322
Waist circumference	.859	-.241
Hip circumference	.860	-.296
Mean_SysBP	.513	.765
Mean_DiasBP	.555	.738

Table 4.7: Component loadings

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Weight	.883	.191
Height	.446	-.117
Waist circumference	.866	.215
Hip circumference	.893	.169
Mean_SysBP	.067	.918
Mean_DiasBP	.117	.916

Table 4.8: Rotated component loadings

Figure 4.4: Component plot in rotated space

Conclusion

In this study, the principal component analysis is utilized to identify two bio metric dimensions which related to body size and blood pressure. The first PC is mainly focused to the weight, waist and hip circumference of human beings. The systolic and diastolic blood pressure readings are emphasized in the second PC. These two dimensions can be used in mathematical modeling to forecast the health risk of human beings.

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